

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The Predictable and Curable Mortality in Europe

Between 2011 and 2020 it decreased by 7.65% for European countries

Avoidable mortality refers to preventable and curable causes of mortality. Preventable mortality refers to the mortality that can be avoided through effective public health and primary prevention interventions. Curable mortality can be avoided through timely and effective health interventions, including secondary prevention and treatment. Total avoidable mortality includes a series of infectious diseases, different types of tumors, endocrine and metabolic diseases, as well as some diseases of nerve, circulatory, respiratory, digestive, parenting systems, some diseases related to pregnancy, child, and perinatal period, one Series of congenital malformations, adverse effects of medical and surgical treatments, a list of injuries and alcohol disorders and drugs. The data are presented as standardized mortality rates, which means that they are adequate to a distribution of the standard age to measure mortality rates regardless of different age structures of the populations.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the mortality avoidable in 2020. Romania is in the first place due to the value of avoidable mortality with an amount of 593.2 units, followed by Lithuania with an amount of 540.06 units and by Hungary with a value equal to 529.99 units. In the middle of the standings there are Germany with an amount of 238.07, followed by Austria with a value of 235.44 units and Finland with an amount of 228.61 units. Norway closes the ranking with a value of 171.75 units, followed by Switzerland with an amount of 164.86 units and Iceland with a value of 156.33 units. The average value of avoidable mortality is in 2020 was 296.71.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of mortality avoidable between 2011 and 2020. Bulgaria is in the first place due to the value of the percentage variation of the mortality avoidable between 2011 and 2020 with an amount of 26.68% equal to a amount of 11.49 units, followed by Serbia with an amount of 11.81% equal to an amount of 51.62 units, and from Poland with a value of 5.94% equal to a value of 23.48 units. In the middle of the standings there are Germany with a value equal to -7.70% equal to an amount of -19.86 units, followed by Portugal with an amount equal to -7.88% equal to a value of -19.22 Unit, and followed by the Czech Republic for an amount of -8.96% equal to an amount of -33.46 units. Norway closes the ranking with an amount of -21.88% equal to an amount of -48.10 units, followed by Iceland with a value of -22.72% equal to an amount of -45.97 units, even to an amount of -23.77% equal to an amount of -65.27 units. Overall, between 2011 and 2020 the value of avoidable mortality decreased by 7.65% equal to an amount of -21.20 units.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The following Clusters are therefore identified or:

- Cluster 1: Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Luxembourg, Malta, Spain, Iceland, Italy, Ireland, Cyprus, Portugal, Belgium, Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Greece, Austria, Denmark, Germany, Finland, Slovenia;
- Cluster 2: Latvia, Romania, Lithuania, Hungary;
- Cluster 3: Croatia, Serbia, Poland, Estonia, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Czech Republic.

From the point of view of the median it appears that the value of C2 is equal to 535.02, while the C3 value is equal to an amount of 418.88 units and C1 is equal to an amount of 204.17 units. It therefore derives the following system or: $C2 > C3 > C1$. Obviously, a high level of avoidable mortality must be considered negatively. It therefore follows that avoidable and curable mortality is very high in the nations of Eastern Europe while it is reduced in the Europe of the West and above all in the countries of northern Europe and Scandinavians.

Network analysis with Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below using the Euclidean distance. The data show the presence of two complex network structures and a simplified network structure. There is a network structure as indicated below or:

- Austria has a connection with Greece for an amount of 0.077 units and with Germany for an amount of 0.11 units;
- Greece has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.077 units and with Germany for an amount of 0.16 units;
- Germany has a connection with Greece for an amount of 0.16 units and with Austria for a value of 0.11 units.

There is also a complex network structure as indicated below or:

- Italy has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.16 units and with Spain for an amount of 0.11 units;
- Spain has a connection with Italy for an amount of 0.11 units and with Cyprus for an amount of 0.15 units, with Iceland for an amount of 0.15 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.083 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Italy for an amount of 0.16 units and with Spain for an amount of 0.15 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.083 units, with Norway for an amount of 0.11 units, with Iceland for an amount of 0.14 units and with the Afrancia for an amount of 0, 15 units;
- Norway has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.11 units and with France for an amount of 0.14 units;
- Iceland has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.15 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.14 units;
- France has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.15 units, with Norway for an amount of 0.14 units and with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.093 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with France for an amount of 0.093 units.

There is a simplified network structure between the following countries or:

- Finland and Denmark are connected for an amount of 0.09 units.

Conclusions. Avoidable and curable mortality decreased in Europe between 2011 and 2020 of 7.65% for the countries considered on average. However, there are countries for which in the same period the curable and avoidable mortality has grown such as Bulgaria, Serbia, and Poland. These values could be higher if considered in the light of Covid 19 which has increased avoidable and curable mortality in each country. The value of avoidable and curable mortality could further decrease in the future due to the use of telemedicine tools. The use of predictive data and algorithms can allow to identify the very critical issues before they are manifested through the analysis of biological parameters. Telemedicine also offers significant support tools for monitoring patients especially suffering from silent killers, such as diabetes and hypertension. In the future it is likely that the healthy population is also subjected to treatment with medical devices for the prediction of the disease and the predictive intervention.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Fuzzy c-Means Clusterization and ANN-MLP Prediction of Malign Breast Cancer in a Cohort of Patients. Available at SSRN.

Massaro, A., Giardinelli, V., Cosoli, G., Magaletti, N., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Prediction of Hypertension Risk. Available at SSRN 4123352.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Giardinelli, V., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022). Original Data Vs High Performance Augmented Data for ANN Prediction of Glycemic Status in Diabetes Patients. Available at SSRN 4082839.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Prediction of Diabetes. Available at SSRN 4135264.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516438>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Individuals with Risk Behaviors in the Consumption of Alcohol in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636364>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est, <https://ilsudest.it/>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Appendix

Variazione Mortalità Evitabile nel Periodo 2011-2020

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Bulgaria</i>	111,49	26,68	17	<i>Czechia</i>	-33,46	-8,96
2	<i>Serbia</i>	51,62	11,81	18	<i>Netherlands</i>	-20,02	-9,08
3	<i>Poland</i>	23,48	5,94	19	<i>Sweden</i>	-19,73	-9,62
4	<i>Romania</i>	29,94	5,32	20	<i>Lithuania</i>	-62,28	-10,34
5	<i>Spain</i>	3,15	1,56	21	<i>Switzerland</i>	-21,00	-11,30
6	<i>Greece</i>	2,43	1,00	22	<i>Liechtenstein</i>	-24,50	-11,70
7	<i>Italy</i>	-3,18	-1,59	23	<i>Slovenia</i>	-40,95	-13,24
8	<i>Cyprus</i>	-5,25	-2,79	24	<i>Malta</i>	-36,81	-15,28
9	<i>Hungary</i>	-26,07	-4,69	25	<i>Ireland</i>	-40,29	-16,01
10	<i>Croatia</i>	-19,61	-4,73	26	<i>Finland</i>	-45,92	-16,73
11	<i>Belgium</i>	-14,85	-5,83	27	<i>Luxembourg</i>	-39,07	-16,77
12	<i>Austria</i>	-14,61	-5,84	28	<i>Latvia</i>	-103,51	-17,08
13	<i>France</i>	-13,12	-6,11	29	<i>Estonia</i>	-86,99	-18,80
14	<i>Slovakia</i>	-30,73	-6,65	30	<i>Norway</i>	-48,10	-21,88
15	<i>Germany</i>	-19,86	-7,70	31	<i>Iceland</i>	-45,97	-22,72
16	<i>Portugal</i>	-19,22	-7,88	32	<i>Denmark</i>	-65,27	-23,77

Ranking per Valore di Mortalità Evitabile

Rank	Country	2020	Rank	Country	2020
1	Romania	593,2	17	Finland	228,61
2	Lithuania	540,06	18	Portugal	224,82
3	Hungary	529,99	19	Ireland	211,42
4	Bulgaria	529,44	20	Denmark	209,32
5	Latvia	502,57	21	Spain	205,59
6	Serbia	488,65	22	Malta	204,17
7	Slovakia	431,28	23	France	201,71
8	Poland	418,88	24	Netherlands	200,43
9	Croatia	395,15	25	Italy	197,05
10	Estonia	375,65	26	Luxembourg	193,94
11	Czechia	340	27	Sweden	185,38
12	Slovenia	268,3	28	Liechtenstein	184,92
13	Greece	245,27	29	Cyprus	182,65
14	Belgium	239,84	30	Norway	171,75
15	Germany	238,07	31	Switzerland	164,86
16	Austria	235,44	32	Iceland	156,33

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Belgium	☆ 254,69	☆ 252,95	☆ 249,36	☆ 236,33	☆ 234,68	☆ 226,38	☆ 220,71	☆ 215,79	☆ 207,37	☆ 239,84
Bulgaria	★ 417,95	★ 442,59	★ 431,63	★ 444,78	★ 442,26	★ 426,5	★ 422,07	★ 414,48	★ 419,74	★ 529,44
Czechia	★ 373,46	★ 364,9	★ 362,66	★ 336,57	★ 341,89	★ 323,26	★ 324,18	★ 319,25	★ 308,6	★ 340
Denmark	☆ 274,59	☆ 269,53	☆ 252,94	☆ 251,22	☆ 242,02	☆ 236,78	☆ 229,93	☆ 224,93	☆ 217,37	☆ 209,32
Germany	☆ 257,93	☆ 252,8	☆ 253,78	☆ 243,34	☆ 249,22	☆ 244,56	☆ 241,05	☆ 240,92	☆ 231,32	☆ 238,07
Estonia	★ 462,64	★ 466,27	★ 436	★ 432,35	★ 418,95	★ 405,36	★ 383,86	★ 386,47	★ 363,52	★ 375,65
Ireland	☆ 251,71	☆ 242,57	☆ 236,64	☆ 230,95	☆ 220,73	☆ 218,24	☆ 202,72	☆ 207,96	☆ 197,91	☆ 211,42
Greece	☆ 242,84	☆ 247,36	☆ 240,91	☆ 236,86	☆ 241,8	☆ 236,31	☆ 235,6	☆ 228,58	☆ 231,11	☆ 245,27
Spain	☆ 202,44	☆ 198,27	☆ 193,81	☆ 188,6	☆ 187,73	☆ 184,65	☆ 181,38	☆ 177,92	☆ 172,5	☆ 205,59
France	☆ 214,83	☆ 208,84	☆ 205,16	☆ 198,33	☆ 199,34	☆ 196,06	☆ 191,95	☆ 188,65	☆ 185,79	☆ 201,71
Croatia	★ 414,76	★ 404,92	★ 384,47	★ 383,23	★ 393,71	★ 371,26	★ 370,95	★ 371,74	★ 360,89	★ 395,15
Italy	☆ 200,23	☆ 197,18	☆ 187,83	☆ 181,87	☆ 184,92	☆ 176,65	☆ 175,07	☆ 168,97	☆ 164,86	☆ 197,05
Cyprus	☆ 187,9	☆ 196,93	☆ 182,29	☆ 182	☆ 189,74	☆ 171,15	☆ 185,41	☆ 182,73	☆ 176,9	☆ 182,65
Latvia	★ 606,08	★ 591,8	★ 581,64	★ 558,07	★ 547,82	★ 535,05	★ 525,32	★ 521,88	★ 485,06	★ 502,57
Lithuania	★ 602,34	★ 591,03	★ 579,86	★ 546,46	★ 556,71	★ 541,71	★ 492,78	★ 478,54	★ 465,99	★ 540,06
Luxembourg	☆ 233,01	☆ 228,08	☆ 231,21	☆ 213,29	☆ 205,48	☆ 211,19	☆ 203,31	☆ 198,04	☆ 177,78	☆ 193,94
Hungary	★ 556,06	★ 542,36	★ 516,64	★ 512,73	★ 518,21	★ 501,24	★ 506,76	★ 501,52	★ 488,54	★ 529,99
Malta	☆ 240,98	☆ 239,33	☆ 209,74	☆ 215,6	☆ 200,85	☆ 202,5	☆ 203,13	☆ 202,51	☆ 186,9	☆ 204,17
Netherlands	☆ 220,45	☆ 218,25	☆ 210,35	☆ 200,87	☆ 205,98	☆ 202,84	☆ 193,19	☆ 193,09	☆ 184,8	☆ 200,43
Austria	☆ 250,05	☆ 250,84	☆ 245,13	☆ 240,9	☆ 245,81	☆ 238,86	☆ 233,26	☆ 232,16	☆ 225,1	☆ 235,44
Poland	★ 395,4	★ 389,06	★ 377,51	★ 355,18	★ 352,57	★ 348,26	★ 351,47	★ 354,93	★ 352,19	★ 418,88
Portugal	☆ 244,04	☆ 236,26	☆ 231,22	☆ 233,11	☆ 228,64	☆ 229,33	☆ 222,28	☆ 221,12	☆ 214,5	☆ 224,82
Romania	★ 563,26	★ 552,27	★ 529,09	★ 526,28	★ 522,99	★ 518,22	★ 512,89	★ 517,47	★ 504,58	★ 593,2
Slovenia	★ 309,25	☆ 297,41	☆ 294,53	☆ 277,59	☆ 284,88	☆ 263,62	☆ 265,47	☆ 252,81	☆ 245,31	☆ 268,3
Slovakia	★ 462,01	★ 458,45	★ 444,41	★ 423,71	★ 435,2	★ 412,2	★ 412,46	★ 406,59	★ 394,63	★ 431,28
Finland	☆ 274,53	☆ 267,92	☆ 259,75	☆ 246,23	☆ 238,15	☆ 242,82	☆ 236,59	☆ 230,22	☆ 222,82	☆ 228,61
Sweden	☆ 205,11	☆ 201,45	☆ 201,33	☆ 194,46	☆ 193,24	☆ 188,91	☆ 184,68	☆ 183,29	☆ 170,18	☆ 185,38
Iceland	☆ 202,3	☆ 192,02	☆ 200,06	☆ 180,86	☆ 192,87	☆ 201,69	☆ 180,48	☆ 178,4	☆ 162,1	☆ 156,33
Liechtenstein	☆ 209,42	★ 179,51	☆ 210,18	★ 151,12	★ 165,82	★ 181,75	★ 158,31	★ 149,74	★ 158,1	★ 184,92
Norway	☆ 219,85	☆ 211,89	☆ 208,06	☆ 195,7	☆ 192,6	☆ 192,01	☆ 180,86	☆ 178,48	☆ 172,18	☆ 171,75
Switzerland	☆ 185,86	☆ 182,15	☆ 179,14	☆ 172,11	☆ 172,39	☆ 163,88	☆ 161,38	☆ 159,51	☆ 153,42	☆ 164,86
Serbia	★ 437,03	★ 426,2	★ 411,26	★ 401,92	★ 417,53	★ 408,12	★ 407,04	★ 398,63	★ 399,83	★ 488,65